

EFFECT OF NICKEL COATED CARBON FIBER AND NICKEL COATED GRAPHITE PARTICLES ON INDUCTION HEATING

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ABSTRACT

Joining of thermoplastic composite parts by induction heating using a susceptor sheet offers great perspective for lightweight applications. A new concept of metal-coated short fibers and metal-coated particles filled Polypropylene (PP) susceptor sheets was developed via melt mixing using double screw extruder and production by Calandering. In this work we investigated the heating behavior of metal-coated fibers and particles. During induction heating experiments, fiber heating by joule loss, dielectric heating, contact resistance heating as well as magnetic hysteresis effect were observed in fiber filled PP, however with particles filled PP only hysteresis effect was observed. Induction heating tests were performed on nickel coated carbon fibers and nickel coated graphite particles using a circular pane cake coil and at frequencies below 1 MHz. Time to reach temperature from 50°C to 120°C was calculated during induction heating experiments. Similar heating trend of fibers and particles filled PP were observed at lower concentrations, however, particles give better heating i.e. takes less to reach at high temperature. At higher concentrations it takes less time to reach at mentioned temperatures was observed in fibers due to above mentioned combined heating effects, while particles follow their trend of hysteresis effect. Electrical conductivity was measured by using four point measuring method and microstructure characterization were performed by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) & X-ray computed microtomography (micro CT).

1. INTRODUCTION

Usage of thermoplastic composites in automotive and aerospace applications has tremendously increased due to various advantages from *properties of thermoplastics*, high stiffness and strength, good fatigue resistance and corrosion resistant [1, 2], from *manufacturing of thermoplastics*, short processing time [3, 4], low cost and ease of repair [5, 6]. Further to above mentioned properties, thermoplastics can be reshaped upon heating unlike thermosets because they don't form crosslinking network. During manufacturing of certain complex parts, they need to be joined in such a fashion that joining method should be fast, reliable and automated so that the industry requirement can be fulfilled.

A product cost depend on materials cost, manufacturing process, and assembly [7], cost effective and reliable methods for joining are favorable. Thermoplastic fusion bonding using induction heating offers an innovative processing, joining and repair technology for composites.

Joining by induction heating will not only save the time but also reduce weight. When conductive and ferromagnetic materials are exposed to an alternating electromagnetic field, heating is obtained by electromagnetic induction. It's based on induced eddy current losses for conductive materials and magnetic polarization effect is based on ferromagnetic hysteresis losses for ferromagnetic materials [8, 9].

Therefore joining of non-conductive materials needs a susceptor medium that can be electrical conductive or ferromagnetic or both. Using electrical conductive material heating can be achieved by

eddy current losses [10, 11], dielectric hysteresis loss [12, 13, 14], or contact resistance [15, 16, 17]. In ferromagnetic materials, heating can be achieved by magnetic hysteresis loss [7] until they reach their Curie Temperature. Using electrically conductive fibers for heating, the condition of closed electrical circuit must be fulfilled, which is usually the case for woven or non-crimp fabric. For a susceptor material consisting of short carbon fibers dispersed randomly in the polymer matrix the condition is fulfilled above percolation threshold.

For Composite materials most of the induction heating experiments so far were performed using unidirectional prepreg materials. Miller et al [11] observed that the major heat source is good electrical contact between crossed plies, and Joule heating in the fibers, while Fink et al [13] observed heat generation is caused by dielectric losses. Yarlagadda et al. [15] observed fiber heating as dominant mechanism, because of the low contact resistance, fiber structure and its type. Kim et al. [16] observed the junction heating as dominant mechanism and high heating can be achieved with available high fiber junctions.

Ferromagnetic particles are also a good source for heat generation [25] and mainly from magnetic hysteresis loss until they reach a percolation threshold where they become conductive. Due to very low aspect ratio, they need higher loading [18] to reach percolation threshold. Added advantage of ferromagnetic particles is their Curie temperature T_C that limits the magnetic properties. Ferromagnetic becomes paramagnetic and stops induction heating process. This is automatic cut off at certain temperature, however only few commonly available susceptor particles have melting range of thermoplastic [19, 20, 21].

Various ferromagnetic particulate, like nickel, iron, magnetite and their alloys, as fillers are being used to obtain heating by induction due to high magnetic properties and Curie temperature [19] makes it self-controlling. Ferromagnetic particles are being used not only in composite materials [23] but also in medical research [22]. Thomas et al. [23] used Iron particles most suitable from heating rate due to higher susceptibility. HDPE melting temperature achieved with 10wt% concentration in 50 seconds, however filler concentration somehow higher for industrial aspect.

The main theme of this work was the fundamental research to NiCCF and NiCG filled thermoplastic susceptor sheet that can work for joining of non-conductive composite materials. This study will elucidate the combined effect of joule loss and junction loss along with hysteresis loss. Due to the nickel coating, it has better electrical conductivity along with hysteresis effect.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials & Manufacturing Process

The Nickel coated short carbon fibers (NiCCF) were purchased from Toho Tenax Co. Ltd. (Tenax®-J HT C903). The PAN-based NiCCF are 6 mm in length, 7,5 μm in diameter and exhibit a density of 2,70 g/cm^3 . The nickel coating thickness is 0.25 μm . Nickel coated graphite particles (NiCG) were purchased from Lomberg GmbH. NiCG were 90 μm in diameter, having a density 3,8- 4,0 g/cm^3 and nickel coating was 60%. Polypropylene (PP) Moplen HP 400R having a density of 0,90 g/cm^3 and a melt flow index of 25 g/ 10min was used as matrix.

Thin sheet of composite were prepared by melt mixing of nickel coated carbon fibers (NiCCF) & nickel coated graphite particles (NiCG) together with the Polypropylene matrix using double Screw Extruder (ZE25A X 44 D, Krauss-Maffei Berstorff GmbH) and subsequent calendering 500 microns thick sheets on a calendering machine for optical films (Dr. Collins GmbH). Different compositions of NiCCF and NiCG were prepared. The main parameters were the processing temperature 220°C, the screw rotation speed of 300 rpm, and the through-put of 9 kg/h. All manufacturing parameters were kept constant for all composites sheets. Feeding of PP granules was into the main feeder; NiCCF and

NiCG were added by a side feeder with a gravimetric controlled dosing system. Vacuum was applied at end of the polymer melt to avoid porosity. The PP/ NiCCF and PP/ NiCG melt came out directly on the calandering rollers for thin sheet forming and rolling at the end of calandering machine.

3. CHARACTERIZATION

3.1 Induction Heating Properties

For induction heating experiments a pancake coil (5 windings, 100 mm in diameter, 6 mm thickness, with an internal cooling) was fed with an alternating current from a generator (Hüttinger TruHeat 5010 MF, Trumpf Hüttinger, Germany). PP/ NiCCF and PP/ NiCG composites sheets (120 * 120 mm² and 60 * 60 mm²) were positioned at a distance of 2 mm from coil. Testing was performed at different frequencies. Generator maximum current was 35 A that transformed to a coil circuit current of 280 A.

3.2 Electrical Properties.

Electrical conductivity of NiCCF/ PP composites was determined according to DIN EN ISO 3915 (1999). A four-point test setup was used with Keithley 2601A electrometer. In four-point test setup, two electrodes were used for power supply and two for measuring the potential difference. The specimens were prepared by stacking several sheets of composite films and subsequent hot pressing to obtain a final thickness of 4 mm. Later on 30 x 10 x 4 mm³ small rectangular samples were prepared by cutting with a band saw. The resin rich surface was removed by grinding and polishing. To reduce the contact resistance, the surfaces were covered with a silver paste (G3692 Acheson Silver DAG 141). The resistivity of the sample was measured and the volume specific conductivity was calculated by

$$\sigma = 1 / \rho = \frac{L}{A R}$$

where, ρ = volume resistivity (Ω -mm), R = measured resistance (Ω), L = distance between electrodes (mm), A = cross-sectional area (mm²) and σ = volume conductivity (Ω^{-1} -mm⁻¹). Five samples were tested and average value of the resistivity in parallel direction (i.e. longitudinal, sheet processing direction from Calandering) obtained. Later on conductivity was calculated from equation (3).

3.3 Morphological Properties.

X-ray computed micro tomography scans (micro CT) were performed using a commercial micro CT (nanotom by Phoenix x-ray systems, Germany) for visualization of the three-dimensional distribution of fibers and particles in the composite. Light microscopical analyses (Diaplan, Leitz, Germany) were carried out to observe macroscopically the fiber orientation and fiber length distribution of NiCCF, using digital images and analysis software (AnalySYS FIVE, Olympus GmbH, Germany). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Zeiss Supra VP40, Carl Zeiss SMT AG, Germany) was performed to obtain further morphological information. Before SEM analysis samples were coated with platinum-gold layer in a sputtering device (Oerlikon Balzers, Liechtenstein).

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY

Figure 1 shows the volume specific conductivity values with respect to filler concentration of the NiCCF samples. The conductivity of NiCCF increases by increasing the filler loading. From 8wt% to 13wt% only a slight increase can be found. But at higher loading a substantial rise in conductivity is observed. Further increasing the filler loading above 18wt% conductivity approaches a plateau. The percolation threshold is in the range of 15wt% filler loading. Besides the good network of fibers at

higher filler loadings, the alignment of fibers in one direction as well as their high aspect ratio and good contact conductivity due to nickel coating is responsible for the high conductivity values. The initial fiber length of 6mm was reduced to approx. 300 μm during processing in the double screw extruder.

Figure 1: Electrical conductivity at various concentration of NiCCF

The volume specific electrical conductivity of the NiCG containing samples was significantly lower, in the range of insulators. Particle sizes were approx.. 90 μm with only a small aspect ratio. The percolation threshold for such particles could be found in literature around 33 vol% [18]. HU Shengfei et al [26] reported for these particles that the percolation threshold is around 40-42wt%.

4.2 Induction Heating Properties

Induction heating properties were analyzed by a variation of the NiCCF and NiCG fillers concentrations. Effects of changing the frequency of the electromagnetic field was studied as well as influence of different microstructures of the sample.

4.2(a) Effect of Susceptor Materials

Two different fillers were used in this study. NiCCF, 6mm long fibers, exhibiting a high aspect ratio and NiCG, 90 micron particles, exhibiting a low aspect ratio. Both these fillers were used separately in various concentrations. Time dependent temperature data was obtained by a IR thermal camera. The obtained temperature was analyzed and compared for different filler concentrations. IR camera recording started 5 seconds prior the induction heating generator starts, however that part has excluded from the graph. In figure 2(a) and (b), time- temperature graph of various filler concentrations of NiCCF & NiCG were compared. In NiCCF heating stopped around 60-70 seconds and in NiCG, heating was stopped around 40-50 seconds, later on cooling takes place.

In NiCCF, Fig. 2(a), increasing the filler concentration increases the heating. Heating was slow at lower concentrations, however a sharp rise can be seen at higher concentrations due to a sudden increase in electrical conductivity, which takes place around 15wt% filler loading as can be found from the measurement of the conductivity of the samples in fig.1. Higher filler concentrations made a good network of interconnecting fibers, therefore increasing the eddy current losses as well as the junction losses [18].

In the NiCG containing samples fig. 2(b), heating was significantly slower at lower concentration, however increases further with increasing the filler concentration. Due to the low filler concentration and low aspect ratio of the NiCG particles, even for the highest concentration, the conductivity was well below the percolation threshold [18]. Therefore the heating is mainly from magnetic hysteresis [7].

Figure 2(a): Effect of filler concentration on heating Graph of NiCCF, tested (@30A & 456 kHz)
Figure 2(b): Effect of filler concentration on heating Graph of NiCG, tested @30A & 456kHz

In figure 3(a), for the NiCCF samples the sample temperature after the first 10 seconds of the induction heating has been plotted versus filler concentration. Induction heating was performed at 30A & 456 kHz. It can be seen that at low concentrations, the temperature achieved was low in this time-interval. Further increasing the concentration, lead to a gradual rise of temperature with concentration until a maximum is reached at approx. 18wt%. However at higher concentrations the temperature decreased again. This may be due to a limited penetration of the electromagnetic field into the sample. Increasing the filler concentration also increases the nickel concentration and increased magnetic permeability.

Figure 3: (a) Effect of filler concentration of Induction Heating (NiCF @ 30A & 456 kHz)
(b) Filler vs Temperature graph of NiCG @ 30A & 456 kHz

In figure 3(b), the temperature after first 10 seconds of induction heating has been plotted versus filler concentration of NiCG samples. Induction heating was performed at 30A & 456 kHz. It can be seen that the overall temperature was significantly lower for all concentrations, with only a slight increase for higher concentrations.

4.3 MORPHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

4.3 (a) Micro CT Imaging

NiCCF / PP composite sheets were processed through calendering therefore the fibers were aligned in processing direction. In micro CT imaging in figure 4(a) aligned fibers can be seen. The magnified cross-sectional view in fig. 4(b) of the same sheet further explains the inside structure. Due to some misaligned fibers a good interconnecting in plane as well as between different layers can be achieved. Therefore a good heating effect can be obtained in such films. Head-tail connections may serve as contact junctions also, that adds to the heating further.

Figure 4: (a) Micro CT image of 15wt% NiCCF / PP (b) Cross-sectional view (c) close view,

Figure 5(a) & (b) are micro CT images of NiCCF and NiCG respectively. It can be seen that the dispersion is very good. The NiCCF are well aligned in processing direction. Only a Few fibers were tilted to small angles at higher concentrations. In figure 5(b) well dispersed NiCG particles can be seen. In NiCG / PP composites, ferromagnetic hysteresis heating was the lone source of heat generation, therefore a good dispersion of the particles in the matrix is required. Proper mixing and uniform dispersion of the particles was achieved due to adequate temperature shear compounding, however possible oxidation of particles cannot be neglected.

Figure 5: (a) 8% NiCCF / PP & (b) 15% NiCG / PP

In figure 6, micro CT images of NiCCF were taken before and after heating for comparison. Before induction heating no misalignment could be observed. And after heating the samples, fibers got misaligned from the melting of the matrix polymer.

Figure 6: (a) 15% NiCCF, before Induction Heating (b) 15% NiCCF After Induction Heating

4.3(b) IR Thermal Imaging

IR thermal imaging is a non-contact temperature measurement technology and it is being used for real time measurement of two dimensional surface temperature fields. Infrared thermography usually consists of a camera, data processing software and a computer. In figure 7, IR thermal images were taken during induction heating experiments. In figure 7(a) heating pattern shows a characteristic typical for the magnetic hysteresis effect, a strong heating in the center of the pancake coil. Although NiCCF's conductivity was around 230 S/m. Due to the nickel coating, the magnetic hysteresis effect was dominating the eddy current loss. At higher concentrations, heating was fast enough nevertheless heating patterns were similar with slightly oval shape as in fig 7(b). This might be due to the aligned fibers. Perfect magnetic hysteresis was obtained during NiCG heating, the same pattern was observed for lower and higher concentrations.

Figure 7: (a) 10wt% NiCCF / PP (b) 13wt% NiCCF / PP (c) 15wt% NiCG / PP

5. CONCLUSION

Nickel coated carbon fiber (NiCCF) and nickel coated graphite particles (NiCG) were incorporated into a polypropylene matrix to form conductive composites. Electrical conductivity of the samples increased by increasing the NiCCF concentration and the percolation threshold was found around 15wt%. With NiCG, due to its low aspect ratio, the percolation threshold is significantly higher, therefore the investigated samples has a conductivity comparable to insulator. A fast heating using induction heating equipment could be achieved by using 15wt% NiCCF, while using the same concentration of NiCG particles lead to a significantly slower temperature increase. The good heating characteristic was achieved due to the high electrical conductivity of the interconnected network of NiCCF and an additional nickel coating, which added extra heating. IR thermal camera images were found useful to distinguish between magnetic hysteresis loss and eddy current loss heating effects.

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